

(c) The C—H out of plane deformation mode identified at $782 \pm 8 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ shows a positive shift due to tightening of the aromatic ring on complexation.

The two absorptions close to each other in the range $400 - 310 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ have been attributed to $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{O})$ giving unequivocal support to coordination through the oxygen atoms of the ligands. The appearance of two Sn—O str. modes is an indication of the different bond strength of the Sn—O linkages, consequently suggesting different basicity of the two donor molecules.

Since in hexa coordinated adducts of tin tetrachloride of the formula $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{L}$, the two monodentate bases occupy *cis* position, the displacement of one of the ligands by another strong base is not expected to produce a major change in the stereochemistry of the adducts.

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New Stable Vanadium(III) Chelates of Some Pyridine Carboxylic Acids

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TRIVALENT vanadium chelates stable in laboratory atmosphere in solid state as well as in solution are of rare occurrence¹⁻³. The present study is

undertaken as a part of our programme on stabilization of normally unstable oxidation states of transition metal ions through ligation to suitable donor molecules. Three extremely stable vanadium(III) complexes of pyridine-2-carboxylic acid, pyridine-2, 6-dicarboxylic acid and pyridine-2, 4, 6-tricarboxylic acid are obtained in the solid state. Hot aqueous solution of the ligands (3.25 m moles) are treated with solid VCl_3 (1 m mole) and stirred vigorously when the following compounds are obtained in good yield:

The compounds are washed with boiled out water and alcohol nearly dried under suction and kept over fused calcium chloride for 48 hours.

Elemental analysis is in accordance with the proposed formulation and is given along with the magnetic moment values at room temperature in Table 1. All the three compounds are stable towards oxidation in the solid state. Solutions of the complexes in boiled out water containing small quantities of the appropriate ligands are fairly stable as is indicated from the unchanged nature of their absorption spectra even after two hours. All the compounds can be recrystallised from concentrated aqueous solutions containing some ligand.

Magnetic moment values at room temperature (300°K) given in Table 1 indicate the presence of two unpaired electrons^{4,5} in all of them. Electronic spectra of the complexes in alcohol and in water in presence of a small amount of the appropriate ligand exhibit two electronic transitions [$27000-25000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$: ${}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$; $13900-12000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$: ${}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$] which are indicative of an octahedral disposition of the donor sites around the $d^3 \text{V(III)}$ species^{1,2,6,7}.

I.R. spectra of the ligand and the complexes were monitored in the $4000-250 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region in CsBr-matrix. Both pyridine-2, 6-dicarboxylic acid and pyridine-2, 4, 6-tricarboxylic acid exhibited the $-\text{COO}$ stretch as a strong band at $1720-1715 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region and pyridine-2-carboxylic acid exhibited the same stretching mode at 1710 cm^{-1} . In the I.R. spectra of the complexes this $1720-1710 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ band is shifted towards lower wave number region ($1675-1665 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) which is indicative of bonding through the carboxyl moiety⁸.

In pyridine derivatives the two bands at $600-640 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (in plane ring deformation) and at $400-415 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (out of plane ring deformation) are

TABLE-1

Sl. No.	Compound	Colour	Vanadium		Nitrogen		μ_{eff} at 300°K (B. M.)
			Found %	Required %	Found %	Required %	
I	V(pic) ₃ ·2H ₂ O	Orange	11.20	11.26	9.19	9.27	2.73
II	V(dipic) ₃ ·2H ₂ O	Yellowish green	8.64	8.76	7.30	7.21	2.66
III	V ₂ (collidH) ₃ ·3H ₂ O	Orange yellow	12.96	13.02	5.42	5.36	2.60

shifted to higher frequency region upon coordination of the ring nitrogen to a metal ion^{9,10}. In the I.R. spectra of all the three complexes these bands were shifted to higher frequency region by 20-35 wave numbers and this has been considered as an evidence of coordination through the heterocyclic nitrogen. The presence of lattice water is exhibited by rather broad bands in the 3500-3200 cm⁻¹ region¹¹.

The above facts indicate that the d² V(III) entity is present in an octahedral donor environment in all the three chelates. To our knowledge these are among the few examples of V(III) chelates which are stable towards oxidation in open atmospheric conditions.

Further studies on the magnetic behaviour at low temperature structure in the solid state and reactivity of the complex species towards various oxidising agents are in progress.

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Study of Some Binary and Ternary Complexes of Praseodymium(III) with Substituted Salicylic Acids

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In our earlier communications^{1,2} we have described investigations on the binary and ternary complexes of Pr(III) with polyhydroxy phenolic ligands. In the present communication we are reporting for the first time the metal-ligand stability constants of ternary complexes (MAL), where M=Pr(III), A=Nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) or N-Hydroxyethylthylenediaminetriacetic acid (HEDTA) or Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) as primary ligand and L-Sulphosalicylic acid (SSA) and 3,5-Dinitrosalicylic acid (DNSA) as secondary ligand (L), by using the modified form of Irving and Rossotti titration technique.

Experimental

The details of the preparation of metal and primary ligand solutions and the instruments used are the same as described in our earlier communications^{1,2}. 0.02M solutions of SSA and DNSA were prepared by dissolving requisite quantities in doubly distilled water, and standardized potentiometrically.

The procedure employed and conditions maintained and the methods of calculations used are also the same as described earlier^{1,2}.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand Stability Constants

The formation curves drawn between \bar{n}_A against pH are found to be extended between 0 to 2 for SSA and 0 to 1 for DNSA in the \bar{n}_A scale indicating the early dissociation of -SO₃H group in SSA and -COOH group in DNSA. The obtained are summarised in Table 1.

Metal-ligand Stability Constants of Binary Complexes

For SSA system the formation curves are found to be extended between 0 to 3 in \bar{n}_A scale indicating